

“Linezolid and Tedizolid: A Solution to Pakistan’s Growing Traditional Antibiotic Resistance”

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study is to observe Linezolid (LZ) and Tedizolid (TZ) activities on Gram positive bacteria - *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile* Gram-negative bacteria – *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and anaerobic bacteria – *Bacteroides fragilis* through disk diffusion method. LZ and TZ are the member of Oxazolidinone which are not very popular in Pakistan and this study will definitely unveil the activity of Oxazolidinone; Why Oxazolidinone should use in Pakistan in contrast to Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria particularly against those bacteria which are resistant to traditional antibiotics.

Methods: LZ and TZ discs were employed for the assessment of antibacterial activity of against Gram positive bacteria - *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile* Gram negative bacteria – *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and Anaerobic bacteria – *Bacteroides fragilis* The content of Tedizolid and Linezolid disk was comprised of 2 µg and 30 µg.

Results: The antimicrobial susceptibility test described that TZ and LZ were very efficacious in contrast to two isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile* showed susceptibility (Zone were For found for TZ 30mm and 29mm, 23mm and 25mm, 31mm and 28mm, 22mm and 24mm, 25mm and 27mm, 21mm and 23mm, 28mm and 26mm, 27mm and 25mm, For LZ 21mm and 25mm, 21mm and 20mm, 22mm and 20mm, 19mm and 21mm, 23mm and 22mm, 18mm and 21mm, 22mm and 25mm, 13mm and 12mm), while resistant showed by the two of the isolates of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* against TZ but showed intermediate for LZ (Zone were found For TZ 13mm, 12mm and 08mm, 10mm, 07mm and 09mm, for LZ; 17mm and 15mm, 8mm and 10mm, 12mm and 10mm), and in two isolates of *Bacteroides fragilis*, susceptibility was observed (zones were found for TZ; 26mm and 28mm, for LZ; 20mm and 19mm).

Conclusion: It is concluded that overall TZ and LZ have better antibacterial activity on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Enterococcus*

faecalis, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile*, *Bacteroides fragilis* while *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed resistance against TZ but intermediate against LZ so in that case LZ is a best choice in terms of both gram positive and negative bacteria.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile*, *Bacteroides fragilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, Tedizolid, disk diffusion, Linezolid, Oxazolidinone.

Abbreviations: LZ (Linezolid), TZ (Tedizolid), MHA (Mueller- Hinton Agar)

INTRODUCTION

The Oxazolidinone class of antibiotics is a recent development in the field of antimicrobials. Higher affinity in terms of results were noted by the Oxazolidinone in contrast to Gram positive microorganisms and produces strong resistance against microbial in clinical manner. The best part of Oxazolidinone is their usefulness and sometimes showed moderate activity towards *Gram negative bacteria* as well (Foti, Piperno et al. 2021). Generally, the group of Oxazolidinone of antibiotics consist on 2-oxazolidione with four alternative ring of phenyl at three points (Buckley, Ndukwe et al. 2023).

LZ and TZ are always the first choice of Oxazolidinone compound which were allowed by Food Drug Administration (El-Kimary, Allam et al. 2023). TZ and LZ are very popular in microbial world because of the inhibition of protein synthesis as well as to treat gram-positive infections. Like LZ, TZ is working with the binding of 23S ribosomal RNA of the 50S subunit, thereby preventing the 70S initiation complex formation and to inhibit protein synthesis (Carena and Stryjewski 2020). Tedizolid has explained potent in vitro activity against multidrug-resistant gram-positive bacteria such as *methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)*, *Streptococcus pneumonia*, and *Vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE)*, including some linezolid-resistant pathogens (Koulenti, Xu et al. 2019). A portfolio of Pharmacokinetics of TZ allows once-daily dosing and easy i.v.-to-oral conversion. In clinical investigation, TZ has not been display the interaction with serotonergic agents in contrast to LZ (Magnani and Mikhail 2017). LZ prevents staphylococci from producing toxins, it acts as a bactericidal antibiotic in vitro even though it has a bacteriostatic effect. Earlier research evaluated that TZ always shows effective against number of significant gram positive cocci, like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus* species, and streptococci (Lan, Lin et. al. 2019). TZ differentiates itself from LZ by integrated a D-ring substituent and a hydroxymethyl group in place of acetamide; both substitutions are vital contributors to its clinical effectiveness versus some linezolid-resistant pathogens (Ndukwe 2024). It has been always noticed that there is a bonding in a huge manner of hydrogen in between TZ with bacterial ribosome by D-ring. That is why, this drug is more favorable in terms to inhibit the synthesis of protein as compare to other Oxazolidinone and allow to give low doses. Time kill curves showed that TZ was having higher activity against staphylococci, enterococci and easily provides bactericidal activity against few streptococci (Wang, Li et al. 2019). Naturally, TZ is synthetic which always helps

to susceptibility of this substance was greatly uniform with different investigations of ingenuous populations of target organisms(Iqbal, Milioudi et al. 2022). TZ have excellent bioavailability which allows healthcare professional to prescribe dose once a day and to easily switch from IV to oral route to treat gram positive bacteria. While it has been observed that LZ and TZ have same advantages but TZ has less SSRI interaction. It has also been observed that TZ gives better result against *Staphylococcus aureus*, which are resistant to LZ especially for short-term use. It is very beneficial for practitioners to prescribe TZ to the diseases like pneumonia etc.(Barbachyn 2018).The main focus of majority of typical laboratory protocols is to evaluate the ability of antibiotic either they suppress or stop the microbial growth(Gajic, Kabic et al. 2022). The principles used in each system determine the classification of antimicrobial susceptibility investigation procedures. Some of them are:

Table 1. Qualitative Outcomes (zone of inhibition) against Gram Positive, Gram negative and anaerobic bacteria

S. No.	Isolates	Disc Diffusion(mm)		
		Susceptible (S)	Intermediate (I)	Resistant (R)
1.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	≥ 21	17-20	< 16
2.	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>			
3.	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>			
4.	<i>Streptococcus Pneumonia</i>			
5.	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>			
6.	<i>Enterococcus Faecium</i>			
7.	<i>Mycobacterium Kansasii</i>			
8.	<i>Clostridium Difficile</i>			
9.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>			
10.	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>			
11.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>			
12.	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>			

Where, the above Table-1 shows, zone of inhibition criteria against Gram positive bacteria- *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile*, Gram-negative bacteria – *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and Anaerobic bacteria – *Bacteroides fragilis*

Material

Autoclave, Balance, Incubator, Laminar air flow cabinet, Microscope, Vernier caliper, Water Bath, Petri dish, TZ disc, LZ disc, Mueller- Hinton Broth (MHB), Nutrient broth.

METHODOLOGY

Disk diffusion method is comprehensively employed to determine the susceptibility of microorganism. The fundamental perspective of disc diffusion technique always rely to inhibit

microbial growth on the top surface of solid medium with antibiotics diffusion by putting disc to the media(Wali, Shah et al. 2022). Afterwards, the zone of inhibition clearly displayed when disc of impregnated antibiotic is employ that explain either microorganism is susceptible to an antibiotic or not. The portion which were not impacted towards normal growth known as Lawn of organism which is easily seen above the zone. A diameter of zone of inhibition demonstrated susceptibility of microbial susceptibility and the quantity of drug in disc showed the good results. The method is applied by following steps;

1. The colonies of the cultures of *isolates* were streaked from the petri plates by using inoculating loop.
2. Now converted them in a tube of MHA broth, then employ incubation at 37°C.
3. Then inoculums turbidity properly uphold, same as McFarland standard's turbidity then incubate by applying lids at 10 to 15 minutes. The MHA plate depth is 4 mm, properly vortexed suspension of culture to achieve maximal mixing.
4. Smoothly dipped cotton swab which is sterilized into the suspension of bacteria and remove any excessive fluid by pressing it.
5. With the help of streaking, the agar should be inoculated with cotton swab, containing the inoculum.
6. The Disks contain 2µgTZ and 30 µg LZonthe plate of inoculated MHA. Each Disk which is firmly pushed downward for the interaction with agar.
7. Agar dishes should incubate towards inverted place.
8. The zone of inhibition was noted from the backside of dishes with reflected light and zone was observed by ruler.
9. The CLSI standard followed for the antimicrobial susceptibilities to indicate the susceptibility, intermediate or resistance of the strain to the TZ and LZ. (See Table 2).

RESULT

Table 2. Isolates Sensitivity Pattern

No.	Isolates	Disc Diffusion(mm)					
		Susceptible(S)		Intermediate(I)		Resistant(R)	
		TZ	LZ	TZ	LZ	TZ	LZ
1.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	30 29	21 25	-		-	
2.	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	23 25	21 20				
3.	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	22 24	19 21	-		-	
4.	<i>Streptococcus Pneumonia</i> <i>Streptococcus Pneumonia</i>	31 28	22 20	-		-	
5.	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i> <i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	25 27	23 22				
6.	<i>Enterococcus Faecium</i> <i>Enterococcus Faecium</i>	21 23	18 21				
7.	<i>Mycobacterium Kansasii</i> <i>Mycobacterium Kansasii</i>	28 26	22 25				
8.	<i>Clostridium difficile</i> <i>Clostridium difficile</i>	27 25	23 21				
9.	<i>Escherichia coli</i> <i>Escherichia coli</i>	-		-	17 15	13 12	
10.	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> <i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	-		-	16 14	08 10	
11.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-		-	12 10	07 09	
12.	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i> <i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	26 28	20 19	-		-	

Where Two isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile* showed susceptibility (Zone were found For

TZ:30mm and 29mm, 23mm and 25mm, 22mm and 24mm, 31mm and 28, 25mm and 27mm, 21mm and 23mm, 28mm and 26mm, 27mm and 25mm, For LZ: 21mm and 25mm, 21mm and 20mm, 19mm and 21mm, 22mm and 20mm, 23mm and 22mm, 18mm and 21mm, 22mm and 25mm, 23mm and 21mm), while two of the isolates of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed resistance (Zone were found for TZ:13mm, 12mm and 08mm, 10mm, 07mm and 09mm. For LZ: 17mm, 15mm and 16mm, 14mm and 12mm, 10mm), and two isolates of *Bacteroides fragilis* were susceptible as well (zones were found for TZ 26mm , 28mm. for LZ 20mm and 19mm)

DISCUSSION

The investigation regarding the antimicrobial susceptibility testing proved that TZ and LZ are very efficient and fruitful to tackle infections against gram positive and gram negative bacteria.

The advantageous aspect of the microbiological clinical laboratory is the essential part of antibiotic testing against isolates of bacteria(Gajdács, Spengler et al. 2017). The basic fundamental part of this protocol is to observe the resistance of bacteria against the drug and observe also either certain strain of bacteria is susceptible, resistant or bactericidal against infections. The main advantages of the disk diffusion protocol are its simplicity, no need of special equipment, very easy to interpret the results by clinicians, and flexible to selection of protocol(Hossain 2024).

The inhibition zones of discs exhibited difference on various microorganism while MICs did not any variations, excluding pneumococci(Tafroji, Margyaningsih et al. 2022). TZ, a new Oxazolidinone, exhibits antimicrobial activity against different Gram-positive pathogens and having more effectiveness versus LZ against pathogens which showed resistant to drugs and wild-type strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* that have chromosomal genes mutations that encode 23 S rRNA or ribosomal proteins L3 or L4(Ruiz-Ripa, Feßler et al. 2021).

CONCLUSION

TZ and LZ both are the best option to treat Gram positive bacteria-*Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii*, *Clostridium difficile* but LZ showed better activity on Gram negative bacteria – *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and anaerobic bacteria – *Bacteroides fragilis*. The zone of inhibition of organisms of this study revealed that the TZ and LZ gave the perfect bactericidal activity against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus Pneumonia*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus Faecium*, *Mycobacterium Kansasii* and anaerobic bacteria – *Bacteroides fragilis* and but only LZ showed response against *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In order to tackle Gram-positive and some Gram-negative bacterial infections, especially those that are resistant to conventional antibiotics, it is concluded that TZ and LZ provide Pakistani healthcare practitioners with useful treatment choices. Their versatility, safety characteristics, and efficacy make them appropriate options for a range of patient populations.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest to disclose.

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